

ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF RURAL-URBAN MIGRATION TO POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN MOROGORO REGION IN TANZANIA, EAST AFRICA

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ABSTRACT: The study titled assessment on the contribution of Rural-Urban Migration to Poverty alleviation in Morogoro region (Wami Dakawa and Mikese). Data collected by using both structured and non-structured interviews. Field observations and secondary data were used to support the truth of collected data using questionnaires. The main sampling procedures were used to obtain two representatives wards. At ward level, 67 respondents each from different households were picked at random for the study.

The main problem which faces the community in rural areas is migration of the people who tends to migrate Rural-Urban. This migration is caused by many factors pull and push factors, push factors include natural calamities like drought in rural areas may force people to migrate, eruptions of diseases, and pull factors it's like unemployment, low wages, poor living conditions and marriage also. So, in this study it needs to explain contribution of this migration Rural-Urban towards poverty alleviation in Morogoro Region of Tanzania (especially in rural areas).

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Research Problem

According to UN (2018), rural-urban migration, for most of human history, most of people across the world lived in small communities. Over the past few centuries and particularly in recent decades this has shifted dramatically. There has been a mass migration of population from rural - urban areas. In visualization we see estimates from the World Urbanization Prospects on the number of people globally who lives in urban and rural areas and in 2017, 4.1 billion of people were living in urban areas. This means over half of the world 55% live in urban settings. According to UNDP (2009), estimates this milestone event when the number of people in urban areas overtook the number in rural settings. A majority and growing proportion of the world's population is living in urban areas. The shares of the world's population living in urban areas is expected to increase from 55 per cent in 2018 to 60 per cent in 2030.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, according to UN, (2007) many poor young farmers from village example, in Southern Mali, leaves his wife and children to find stable employment in capital city of Bamako. What he finds is an unrewarding reality that leads him from small job to small job, only earning about US 22cents per day. These jobs range from selling sunglasses, together shining shoes, to driving a rickshaw. approximately one person in two subsist on less than US \$1.25 per day, with approximately 70 percent living in rural areas. The situation is worse for young women, many who have migrated to escape forced and early marriage as they face particular barriers to the Labor market, much of which were attributable to cultural attitudes of men. They may find work in domestic setting and in small business. More commonly, many girls were exploited because they were young, easily manipulated, unaware of their rights, and afraid to expose their negligent employers.

In Tanzania, the location, size and distribution of major urban centers in Tanzania is almost entirely the product of German and British decision in the late 19th century to the first few decades of the 20th Century. There is a direct relationship between poverty and migration high poverty and high migration, thus people may migrate out of poverty in order to improve their livelihoods or to migrate into more vulnerable

situations and thus become further impoverished through their movement. According to Kabeer, (2000), migration is not an atomistic reaction to economic or environmental pressure, but it's embedded in societal rules and norms. But according to Aikaeli (2008) added that individuals and groups may remain chronically poor by adopting migration as a livelihood strategy or alternatively, may benefit from migration and move out of chronic poverty. At the same time, there were those whose social, cultural, economic and political exclusion make them unable to move potential migrants and those who choose not to move committed non- migrants and who subsequently stay put albeit in an environment characterized by out migration.

Thus, not everyone is similarly mobile for a range of reasons which include lack of knowledge about other places and opportunities outside the confines of their own geographical and cultural environment, social and cultural environment, social and cultural ties which bind them to their home place, physical immobility, gender and age (Aikaeli, 2008). Thus, migration is best understood as a cause and consequence of chronic poverty for those who move as well as for those who stay behind and consequently, role of migration in chronic poverty is relationship between mobility and immobility and more generally the interconnectedness of people and places (Aikaeli, 2008).

This research problem intends to assess the rural - urban migration on poverty alleviation in Morogoro region (Wami Dakawa and Mikese), where there is high rate of population in urban than rural areas in the scale of migration present a paradox, for many migration does not necessarily make migrants better off ,indeed some become further impoverished by moving from one place to another.

Statement of the Research Problem

There were scientific researchers' explanation and studies that have been conducted in this region focusing on understanding how rural to urban migration encourage poverty alleviation especially to the origin residential (rural) at Mikese and Wami Dakawa. The late of youth migrate from rural areas to urban in Morogoro region (Wami Dakawa and Mikese has been increasing due to the reasons of finding job opportunities at the level of domestic work up to the small business which helps them in their needs and families.

This migration of the people from rural to urban, sometimes it has benefits to their origin place due to the improvement of social service like hospitals, schools and transport way after getting wealth to the urban area also to send back remittance to their families which helps to reduce level of poverty to the rural areas. But also, the Government of the United Republic of Tanzania and other stakeholders in the private sectors were taking various efforts to control and to reduce rural - urban migration as well as poverty reduction to the youth by directing many projects in rural areas and by improving agricultural sector which can increase employment opportunities and promote livelihoods for rural youth. These efforts include creating favorable policy and legislative environment for attracting domestic as well as foreign investments to increase employment opportunities.

According to Kilonzo, (2005) majority of the youth both female and male move from rural to urban areas searching for better life but in reality they sometimes end up living in poorer conditions and other groups end up practicing illegal activities e.g., injection of drug user. Others end up living in squatter settlements which were overcrowded and with poor sanitation. Also, rural to urban migration can increasing crimes rates, unemployment and underemployment due to inadequate social services and popular pressure of political systems, the piece of the nation can be decrease or jeopardized according to Simler, (2006).

Therefore, This study intends to assess the contribution of rural-urban migration among people in rural areas of Morogoro region, Tanzania.

The Research Study Objectives

General Objective

The main objectives of this study is to assess contribution of rural - urban migration towards poverty alleviation among people in Morogoro region rural areas, Tanzania.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this research study were follows;

- i. To identify the push factors influencing people to migrate to the urban areas from rural areas of Morogoro Region, Tanzania.

- ii. To identify the impacts of rural - urban migration both negative and positive impacts especially to the rural areas in Morogoro region.
- iii. To identify contributions of rural - urban migration toward poverty alleviation to the rural areas Morogoro region.

Research Question

- i. What are the push factors influencing rural - urban migration among people of rural areas Morogoro region?
- ii. What are the impacts caused by rural - urban migration among people of rural areas rural areas Morogoro region?
- iii. What are the contribution of rural - urban migration to the poverty alleviation in rural areas of Morogoro region?

The Significance of the Research Problem

The study has got both significance to the individuals and government due to the policy implications. In case of individuals, it helps to know what they are supposed to do especially to their origin place for those who migrate from rural to urban, this is due to send back remittance to their families and to know their right when they come to migrate and work to urban areas as domestic worker and to make business. In case of Government policy, they should plan and make different motivation and projects in order to help this people who migrate for the case of finding better life in their origin place, this helped people to work hard and to make changes to their origin areas than to shift in urban. In doing so, poverty alleviation be easy in origin areas where people come from through migration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptualization of the Key Terms

Poverty

According to FAO (2018), billions of people around the world live in extreme poverty. Nearly 10 percent of the world's population that is almost 1 billion people living below the World Bank Poverty line of \$1.90 per day. And almost half the World (nearly 4 billion people) lives with a household income below \$2.50 a day.

The extremely poor live without support, on the sidelines, watching economic growth and prosperity pass them by, they are shunned by the World economy. They live lives abundant in scarcity. Even the environment attacks poor people, when nature strikes the world's poor suffer the most. The Sustainable Development Goals, adopted in 2015 by the United Nations, are the most comprehensive and ambitious poverty reduction plan the World has embarked upon. They expand the scope of the World community's previous effort to eradicate the burden poverty places on the World Population.

Poverty reduction approaches in developing countries over the past 50 years. Historically, the term poverty reduction in developing countries has been used purposely to refer to direct interventions in the provisions of facilities that are lacking and finding solutions to deficiencies in infrastructure with investments from international lending agencies (Singleton, 2003). Poverty reduction approaches has evolved over the past 50 years in response to a deepening understanding of the complexity of development (Domfeh, (2009). For example, in Africa has been identified as the only region where incidence of poverty has been increasing overtime, with the continent's share of global poverty expected to reach 82% in 2030 (Alkire, 2011; Chandy et al, 2013). At the same time official United Nations statistics indicate that developing countries are expected to experience an unprecedented rate of urbanization in foreseeable future (UNDESA/PD, 2012) amidst persistent poverty conditions (Cobb in ah et al., 2013; Garland et al., 2007; United Nations, 2013).

For instance, the urban population of Africa, which was about 400 million in 2010, is projected to more than triple to about 1.3 billion in 2050 according to UNDESA/PD (2012).

Migration

According to Ernesto (2018), migration is defined a broadly as a permanent or semi-permanent change of residence, no restriction is placed upon the distance of the movement upon the voluntary or involuntary nature of the act, every act of migration involves an origin, a destination and an intervening set of obstacles. Also, migration as the movement of people from one place in the World to another for the purpose of taking up permanent or semi-permanent residence. Example of semi-permanent

residence, would be the seasonal movement of migrant's farm laborers, or sometime people choose to move somewhere this are voluntary migration or others they are forced to move somewhere which is involuntary migration according to National Geographic Society (2005).

Review of Theoretical Literature Review

Introduction

There are several relevant theories related to the subject under discussion but in the case of the study a researcher chosen few theories to represent a study and directly related to a subject matter. The theories chosen and law are the Neoclassical economic theory, Dual Labour market theory, Ravenstein's law and Lee's law. Common to these theories and laws is the fact that migration to urban areas has been viewed in terms of economic determinants.

Dual Labor Market Theory

According to W. Arthur Lewis in Labor Theory, refers to the theory that the American economy or labor market states that migration is mainly caused by pull factors in more developed countries and W. Arthur Lewis was enumerated in his article entitled and it based on the factors of Rural to Urban Migration as first objective of the study. This theory assumes that the labor markets in these developed countries consist of two segments which is primary, it requires high- skilled labor and secondary which is very labor - intensive but requires low- skilled workers. This theory assumes that migration from less developed countries into more developed countries is a result of a pull created by a need for labor in the developed countries in their secondary markets. Migrants' workers are needed to fill the lowest rung of the labor market because the native laborers do not want to do these jobs as they present a lack of mobility. This creates a need for migrant workers, furthermore, the initial dearth in available labor pushes wages up, making migration even more enticing.

Also, there is difference between primary and secondary labor market. In addition to the primary Sectors, these markets also tend to be unionized which has a big impact on both the job security and benefits employees have access to. Moreover, in economies like U.S, primary market jobs often filled by native residents who were

born and raised in the divided market. so, the secondary sphere tends to associate with more negative qualities like minimum wage, poor working conditions, little or no opportunities for career advancement and unreliable job security. Again, second market jobs are often filled by migrants, ethnic minorities, and those with troubled upbringings or disadvantaged backgrounds. Because, secondary market laborers tend to lack the reliability, skills, education, or knowledge of those in the primary sphere, many secondary sectors jobs have frequent turnover.

Economic dependence of former colonies still remains on mother countries. This view of international trade is controversial, however, and some argue that free trade can actually reduce migration between developing and developed countries. It can be argued that the developed countries import labor - intensive goods which causes an increase in employment of unskilled workers in the less developed countries, decreasing the outflow of workers, the export of capital - intensive goods from rich countries to poor countries also equalize income and employment conditions, thus also slowing migration. In either direction, this can be used to explain migration between countries that are geographically far part because its relevance issue.

Relevance

In Urban most of the entrepreneurs and small business they are come from rural areas in order to find money and to send back remittance to their families. So, is the economic factor and also domestic workers especially for young girls they are doing in Urban areas. This theory is relevance in such way as economic factor for them to migrate from they are origin residential in the objective number one.

Weakness

He based only on the economic factor as pull factor and he fail to show on which way this people they are use up to get employment opportunities because most of them they are illiterate people and incase of economic level, it needs person who understand on what he or she doing at the company or any work organization.

Empirical Studies

The following is the summary of empirical review which involves authors, years published, theme, weakness and relevance; -

Author	Year	Theme	Weakness	Relevance
Justin Visagie and Ivan Turok	(2017)	Impacts of rural-urban migration	Do not explain about the factors which leads Rural Urban migration.	It is relevance in societies where the impacts of this migration sometimes in because of war which force people to migrate as refugees in the areas of destination. Objective number two.
Chukwuedozie K. Ajaero & Patience C.	(2013)	It explains about the effects of rural to urban migration	Do not explain about negative impacts of rural-urban migration in rural areas after this people to migrate to the urban areas.	It is relevance due to the improvement of those rural areas due to those who tend to migrate and to

				send back that remittance to their origin residential.
Article according to Awoh AB.	(2016)	Contribution of rural to urban migration	There is no weakness in this contribution explained.	It is relevance due to those contribution explained and this migration at the some large it is positive impacts the rural areas due to the improvement of their attitudes and ideas in different matter so as to gain development.

W.Arthur Lewis		Explain about the pull factor which contribute people to migrate rural to urban which is economic factors and it involve employment opportunities	He based only on the economic factor as pull factor and he fail to show on which way this people they are use up to get employment opportunities because most of them they are illiterate people.	In Urban most of entrepreneurs and small business they are conducting with this people who migrate from rural so is the economic factor and also do domestic work especially for young girls they are doing in Urban area as economic factor for them to migrate from they are origin residential.
Willium Stanley Jevons, Carl Menger and Leon Walras	19 century	Economic factor of Rural to Urban Migration	They are failing to explain about others who get humiliation in Urban areas because of wage payment this because people in Urban areas they have tendency to ignore people from	It is true due to the wage difference it pulls a person to shift from rural areas to urban areas. In Urban areas people they are paid according to the
			Rural because they are know that this people is uneducated.	work they are doing which are differ with rural areas who depend on the trend of production due to the farmer owners.
Wenger, C. and Abdulfatah, D.	(2019)	Impacts of Rural-urban migration	They are look only on the impact of Rural-urban migration without explain those causes which leads this impact of Refugees in the area of destination	Relevance in the objective number two which is the impacts of rural to urban migration

Conceptual Framework

In an attempt to put this study in context, the conceptual framework as shown in was developed for the sake of getting information relevant to the study objectives and to identify the measurable variables. The dependent variable which is the poverty alleviation to the rural -urban migration is influenced by independent variable which includes rural-urban migration in Wami Dakawa and Mikese. Also, there are background variable that are responsible for determining the influence of independent variables these are age, sex, marital status, education and employment.

Fig 01: Conceptual Framework
Source: Researcher (2025)

Research Gap

Many studies have been undertaken in different regions and various research methods were applied. However, there some key issues that have not yet been addressed by researchers concerning rural -urban migration towards poverty alleviation due to the most research study have focused on the impacts of those who migrants to the area of destination without saw how this migration it affects at their

origin areas. Where in origin areas there is many impacts of this rural-urban migration like, shortage of man power to stabilize economy of that place because those man power tends to move to their origin, poor social services, this because those who supposed to construct and to make changes of this services they are tends to migrants to the urban areas, extremely poverty among people from origin who have no ability to migrants into another area especially Elders.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY (MATERIALS AND METHODS)

This chapter described in details the whole methodology can use in conducting research study for the intention of obtaining adequate information. Despite that this chapter addresses the research. sample use, research design, data collection methods, and instruments, also indicates the population study area and the procedures of data collection and analysis.

Research Design

According to Ahuja Ram (2010), research design, is the arrangement of conditions for the collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy and procedures. Research design is the plan, structure, strategy and investigation concave so as to obtain ensure to search questions and control variance. In this research used mixed approach design this means both quantitative and qualitative design, this because quantitative research is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics, it is used to quantify attitudes opinions, behaviors and other define variables and generalize results from a larger sample population. Quantitative data collection method includes various forms of surveys, face-to-face interviews, telephone interview and systematic observations so it contains fact and quickly information of the research problem. In qualitative research it used to gain understanding of underlying reasons, opinions and motivations. It provides insights into the problem or helps to develop ideas or hypothesis for potential quantitative research (Susan,2011).

Description of the Study Areas

This study conducted in Morogoro region (Wami Dakawa and Mikese), Morogoro Region is one of Tanzania's 31 administrative regions. The regional capital is the

municipality of Morogoro. According to the 2012 national census, the region had a population of 2,218,492, which was higher than the pre census projection of 2,209,072. Morogoro Rural District is the one of the six districts of the Morogoro region of Tanzania. Morogoro Rural District covers about 19,056 square kilometers (7,358 Sq. mi). It is bordered to the North and East by the Pwani Region, to the South of Kilombero District, to the southwest by the Kilosa District and to the West by the Mvomelo District and the Morogoro Urban District. In this research dealt with two villages in Rural

THE MAP OF TANZANIA WHICH SHOW MOROGORO REGION AND ITS WARD

Figure 2: The Map of Tanzania showing Morogoro Region and its Wards

Source: URT, 2025

Areas, Mikese and Wami Dakawa. Mikese rural area the distance up to the urban area it took 32.3 km from Mikese to Morogoro Bus Stand. In the census of 2002 population of people in Mikese were 18,112 but up to the 2012 census population has declined to reach 15,569 due to the Migration of the people from rural area to the Morogoro Urban areas. 23 Kilometers from Areas which contains (Mikese ward and Dakawa) Morogoro Urban District

Study Population

The research constitutes all people from the two wards in Morogoro Rural areas, the ward is Mikese ward and Wami Dakawa and all migration officers from this ward so as to get enough information, combined both Youths, women, men and Elders

Sample and Sample size

Sample, Is the group of people or objects or items that are taken from a larger population for measurement. Sample should be representative of the population to ensure that generalized the finding from the research sample to the population as whole. In research sample it is necessary to use because it is impractical to study the whole population. For example, suppose we wanted to know the average number of youths who migrate from rural to urban it needs to choose sample of youth and to see how much they migrate. Sample size, Is the act of choosing the number of observations or replicates to include in a statistical sample. The sample size is an important feature of any empirical study in which the goal is to make inferences about a population from sample

The sample size of the study area determined by using this formula

$$S = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= sample size

N= Number of households -14.14 acceptable sampling error at 90• confidence interval = 0.1 s = sample size

Therefore, from the formula;

$$S = N/1+N (e)^2$$

$$S = 15,569 / 1 + 2,218,492 \times 0.1$$

$$S = 99$$

Ratio of population sample in each ward

$$\text{Mikese} = 15,569 / 2218492 \times 99$$

= 70 population sample in Mikese ward

$$\text{Dakawa} = 15223 / 2218492 \times 99$$

= 67 population sample in Dakawa.

Sampling Procedures

Sampling procedure, Is a process of choosing a sub - group from a population to participate in the study. Sampling procedure it is the process of selecting number of individuals for a study in such a way that individuals selected represent the large group from which they selected Ogula, (2005). The study focused in probability sampling, this because probability sampling everyone has an equal chance of being selected. This scheme is one in which every unit in the population has a chance (greater than zero) of being selected in the sample. This study involved those office of migration in rural areas where is Wami Dakawa and Mikese and from Morogoro city council for a Minister of migration to check out that information about sample who migrate from rural to urban area for the difference reasons.

Sampling Techniques

In this study used questionnaire, documents observations from the migration officers, interview and also focus group discussion methods of data collection techniques. In the case of questionnaire involves open and close ended questions this special for educated individuals and interviews focused to both of them. The reason of choosing these techniques it is because help to get easy that information about the research problem went to deal with.

Data Collection Instruments

Documents Review

The researcher used those documents records from migration officers in both sides rural and urban in order to see the trending of migration of this people at whole time and to see the challenges facing them and how they contribute to alleviate poverty from they are origin residential areas. The documents review includes, newspapers, books, research paper literature review, business Magazines, documented records, organization reports, journals and government survey those helped to get factors, impacts and contributions as objectives of the research study.

Interviews

According to Neale (2006), is the qualitative research technique which involves conducting intensive individual interviews with a small number of respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program or situation. This technique easy to the rural area where many people are not educated, so they give out information which help in research study and to get solutions of those factors which leads migration Rural - Urban Migration.

Questionnaires

According to McNabb, (2008), is the questionnaire is a reformulated written set of questions to which respondents record their answers. Questionnaires used on the basis that the variables under the study cannot be observed for instance the views, opinions, perceptions and feelings of respondents, it involves both open ended questions and closed ended questions which respondents answer. The researcher used questionnaire because, it helps in collecting large amount of data within a very short time and involving large number of respondents which leads to get answers of those research questions. This method was easy to answer that personal background which can be the factor which influences Rural-Urban migration.

Focus Group Discussion

According to Patricia (2011), is the process of gathering people from similar background or experiences together to discuss a specific topic of interest. This it is a

form of qualitative research where questions asked about their perceptions attitudes, beliefs, opinions or ideas. Used this method so as get clear information from majority and direct fact of a study also, improve experience of a research study. This was easy to organize respondents due to their intentions. This method answered quickly information which comes to answer that contribution of rural-urban migration towards poverty alleviation.

Validity and Reliability

According to Fiona (2019), validity and reliability are concepts used to evaluate the quality of research. It indicates how well a method, techniques or test measures something. Reliability is about the consistency of a measure, and validity is about the accuracy of a measure. It is important to consider reliability and validity when creating a research design, planning methods and writing results especially in quantitative research.

Data Collection Procedure

Is the process of gathering and measuring information on variables of interest, in an established systematic fashion that enables one to answer stated research questions, test hypothesis, and evaluate outcomes. In this study researcher before measuring and gathering information of the study asked the permission letter from the Institution Mwenge Catholic University and the letter from migration office of the Wami Dakawa and Mikese rural areas and at the Morogoro City Council, so as to be introducing to the respondents went to deal with, then the researcher going to the selected ward to choose sample of at list 33 to participate in providing information about the research study.

Data Analysis

Is the process of systematically applying or logical techniques to describe and illustrate, condense, recap, and evaluate data. In data analysis comprised qualitative research and quantitative research and each method has their own techniques. Interview and observations are forms of qualitative research while experiments and

surveys are quantitative research. Therefore, the researcher used this so as to makes data more explicit and, in the manner, to be easily understood.

Ethical Consideration in Research

This was how a researcher considered those people who going to deal with, consideration is the all about to base in all gender where is male and female, to consider those Elders and to give them priority of providing information about the research study, and a researcher made sure participations of all sample went perfect with respectfully to each other without contradiction to anyone.

PRESENTATION, INTERPRETAION AND DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Introduction

This chapter present data by using table form which show that demographic information which involves sex and gender, factors for rural to urban migration, impacts for migration and contribution of rural to urban migration. Also, in interpretation its involves analyzing of presented table by showing percentages and frequencies and lastly, discussion of the findings of the study shows what“s the researcher saw in the area of study aimed to examine the assessment on the contribution of Rural-Urban Migration to Poverty alleviation in Mikese and Wami Dakawa in Morogoro region.

Demographic Information for Respondents

Introduction

This section shows the Sex of respondent, age, marital status, level of education, size of household, major source of income for livelihood and estimated income per year. Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented on table 4.2.1

Demographic Information of Respondents of Age and Sex

This section shows the Sex of respondent and age the Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented below.

Demographic Information Of respondents

This section shows the level of education and the Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented on chart 4.2.3

Source Field Data (2025)

Level of education indicated that no formal education were 32 (32.3%), primary education 31 (31.3%) ordinary secondary education were 20 (20.2%), certificate or diploma 16 (16.2%). Therefore study shows that no formal education were many than other education group.

The overall pattern that emerges about the Wamachinga (small-scale businessmen) is that they are a "cohort-specific rural-urban migrants" (Becker and Grewe, 2016), in relation to such social indicators as age, education, sex, religion, marital status, and previous working experience. Mbonile (1995b: 39) writes "it is the spatial and socio-economic dimensions. which encourage migration", rural-urban migration depend on the ecology, the national economy and the international market. Significantly, the countryside is the locus of reproduction for capitalist production in the city.

Shows Gender of Respondents

The table below shows gender of the respondents and has been categorized into male and female in term of Pie chart.

Source Field Data (2025)

A researcher found that the respondents participated in the study indicated male were 57 (57.6%), female 42 (42.4%). According to Uyangoda, J. (2016) who implied that Demographic Information of respondents“ shows that male was many compared to female therefore enabled to provide information about the study problem in that villages.

Age of Respondents

The table below shows the age of the respondents in term of years

Age of respondents	F	%
18-25 years	11	11.1
25-45 years	43	43.4
45-60 years	32	32.3
60-80 years	13	13.1

Source Field Data (2025)

Age of the respondents shows those 18-25 years was 11 (11.1%), 25-45 years were 43 (43.4%), 45-60 years were 32 (32.3%), and 60-80 years were 13 (13.1%).

The study is simultaneously with Jacob, (2016) he agreed that most of the young people are highly affects by rural urban migration due to that hinder the strategies of poverty alleviation caused by shortage of labour in the community.

The dependency approach explains rural-urban migration as a function of a complex web of interacting elements concerned not only with why people migrate but also with all the implications and ramifications of the process. Migration, according to this approach results from a series of adjustments between rural control sub-systems based on kinship, overpopulation and environmental deterioration and one connected to residential and occupational incentives.

Table 4.2.4 Demographic Information of Respondent’s Marital Status

This section shows the Marital Status the Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented below.

Table 4.2.4 shows Marital Status

	F	%
Single	10	10.1
Married	55	55.6
Divorced	10	10.1
Widowed	8	8.1
Separated	0	0.0
Total	16	16.2

Source Field Data (2025)

Also, marital status of the respondents shows that single were 10 (10.1%), married were 55 (55.6%), divorced were 10 (10.1%), widowed were 8 (8.1%), separated were 16 (16.2%). Neale, (2016). Who married one in the area of study were many if you compare with other in the tables above and implied that married people were involved much to give the answer about the study.

Demographic Information of Respondent’s Size of Household

This section shows the respondents size of household the Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented on

Table 4.2.5 shows Size of Household

The table below shows household size of the respondent

	F	%
2 persons	3	3.0
3-5 persons	40	40.4
6-8 persons	28	28.3
9-11 persons	14	14.1
12 persons	13	13.1

Source Field Data (2025)

Also, size of the house hold where two persons were 3 (3.0%), 3-5 person were 40 (40.4%), 6-8 persons were 28 (28.3%) 9-11 persons were 14 (14.1%) 12 persons were 13 (13.1%).

Figure income per year

Source Field Data (2025)

And finally estimated income per year indicated that less than 200,000/= were 54 (54.5%), 200,000 - 500,000/= were 34 (34.3%) and more than 500,000/= were 7 (7.1%). Therefore, the table shows that less than 200,000/= were many than another group in the table above.

According to Boyce, C. (2016), who show that many people in this villages have extreme poverty thus why they are shifted from rural to urban so as to find income for they are survive with they are family.

Demographic Information Source of Income for Livelihood

This section shows the Source of income for livelihood the Description on this identified aspect have been presented and discussed. The find of demographic information of respondent are presented on table 4.2.6

Source of Income for Livelihood	F	%
Salary/wage	20	20.2
	15	15.2
Income generating project		
	42	42.4
Farming/Livestock		
	21	21.2

Source Field Data (2025)

The major source of income for your livelihood indicated that salary wage was 20 (20.2), income generating project 15 (15.2%), farming or livestock 42 (42.4%), others were 21 (21.2%).

The study by (Maliyamkono and Bagachwa, 2017). The particular form of informal economy they are engaged in is conventionally referred to as petty trading (The so called wamachinga petty traders roam about the streets selling a variety of items ranging from second hand clothes to new manufactured household supplies. This study focuses on this group of petty traders.

Table 4.3 Information on Existing Situation Concerning with Rural to Urban Migration Towards Poverty Alleviation

The table shows the factors which leads people to migrate from Rural to Urban and the respondents responds on yes and no question

Variables	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
Factors which lead people to migrate from Rural to Urban	91	91.9%	8	8.1%

Source Field Data (2025)

Most of the respondents implied much on **YES** in the 91 (91.9%) percent that there are factors which leads people to migrate from Rural to Urban include poverty,

inequitable land distribution, environmental degradation, high vulnerability to natural disasters, and violent conflicts while urban pull factors include better employment and education opportunities, higher income, diverse services, and less social discrimination in the cities this was why respondents respond in the high percent.

Introduction

The first research question asked to the respondents that Information on existing situation concerning with rural to urban migration towards poverty alleviation

Table 4.3.7 Information on existing situation concerning with rural to urban migration towards poverty alleviation

	SD	D	U	A	SA					
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Unemployment	1	1.0	1	1.0	5	5.1	28	28.3	64	64.6
Refreshments	1	1.0	6	6.1	20	20.2	34	34.3	38	38.4
Physical barriers (Drought, Earthquake)	2	2.0	2	2.0	18	18.2	27	27.3	50	50.5
Rural poverty	2	2.0	0	0.0	11	11.1	29	29.3	56	56.6
Personal decision	1	1.0	1	1.0	8	8.1	44	44.4	44	44.4
Low price of agricultural products	2	2.0	2	2.0	11	11.1	46	46.5	36	36.4
Lack of Transport connectivity	2	2.0	3	3.0	12	12.1	27	27.3	49	49.5

Source Field Data (2025)

The result shows that 64 (64.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed that Unemployment is concerning with rural to urban migration towards poverty alleviation and It implies that an increase in unemployment benefits and income in the informal sector attracts more labor from the agricultural sector to the informal sector, thus driving up wages in the agricultural sector, 38 (38.4%) of the

respondents responds agreed that Refreshments rural to urban migration towards poverty alleviation, 50 (50.5%) of the respondents agreed that physical barriers (Drought, Earthquake) leads to rural to urban migration, 29 (29.3%) were agreed that Rural poverty caused by rural to urban migration most of labour migrate to urban for searching jobs, 44 (44.4%) of the respondents were agreed that Personal decision influences much on rural to urban migration due to the fact that they decide to live urban for better life than in rural areas, 46 (46.5%) of the respondents agreed that Low price of agricultural products influence people to move to urban life. And finally, 45 (49.5%) were agreed that Lack of Transport connectivity.

The study is supported by Ellis (2016) who said that urban centers are increasing in population; rural areas are decreasing in population. For these reasons, there is a widespread concern that the rates of rural-urban migration should be slowed. But more importantly to policy makers is that urban unemployment and high rates of urbanization pose strong social and political challenges for reducing the flow of migrants to urban areas. This paper discusses the challenges that face rural-urban migration. It analyzes migration theories that provide theoretical reasoning behind rural-urban migration.

Table 4.2.3 Impacts of Rural-Urban-Migration

The table show the Impacts of Rural-urban-migration in which respondents supported to answer on yes and no question in the table below

Variables	Yes		No	
	F	%		%
2b) impacts of Rural- Urban Migration	92	90.9%	7	7.1%

Source Field Data (2025)

Most of the respondents were responds much on **YES** that there impacts of Rural-Urban Migration in the 92 (90.9%) percent there impacts of rural- urban migration like The movement poses some problems in the rural as well as in the urban Centre even though; there are benefits derivable from it.

When I was conducting interview guide in the area of study with the question of Does the migration has any impacts to both side Rural and Urban areas respondents

responds that „there are several impact of migration to both urban and rural areas like the impact of rural-urban migration was a rapid deterioration of the rural economy leading to chronic poverty and food insecurity, These arise mainly due to excessive drain of youth from the rural populace thus leaving only the older and aged members to constitute the labour force of the rural area; people tend to be pulled to the areas of prosperity and pushed from areas of decline“

Similar views are held by other observers Cooker (2013), taht the dependency approach explains rural-urban migration as a function of a complex web of interacting elements concerned not only with why people migrate but also with all the implications and ramifications of the process. Migration, according to this approach results from a series of adjustments between rural control sub-systems based on kinship, overpopulation and environmental deterioration and one connected to residential and occupational incentives.

Introduction

The question asked the Impacts of Rural-urban-migration like Natural resource depletion, environmental pollution, earning disparities, redundancy, urban expansion; Migration has its own positive and negative consequences on the place of departure and destination.

Table 4.3.8 Impacts of Rural-urban-migration

	SD		D		U		A		SA		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Shortage of Labor	5	5.1	0	0.0	3	3.0	29	29.3	61	61.6	
Decrease Rural populations	5	5.1	1	1.0	6	6.1	36	36.4	51	51.5	
Increase child labor	6		6.1	4	4.0	11	11.1	26	26.3	52	52.5
Increase Workload	5		5.1	4	4.0	17	17.2	44	44.4	29	29.3
Decrease the quality of education & health services in the community	5		5.1	2	2.0	11	11.1	52	52.5	26	26.3
Unemployment	5	5.1	1	1.0	7	7.1	23	23.2	58	58.6	

Source: Field Data (2025)

The results shows that 61 (61.6%) respondents strongly agreed that it led to Shortage of Labor the urban labor market the demand for and supply of urban social services, 51 (51.5%) of the respondents were strongly agreed that it led to Decrease Rural populations due to Poverty, food insecurity, lack of employment, climate change and environmental degradation are among the root causes of migration. of migration. By 2050, over half of the populations in the least developed countries still live in rural areas, 52 (52.5%) of the respondents were strongly agreed that led to Increase child labor, 44 (44.4%) of the respondents were agreed that led to Increase Workload, 52 (52.5%) of the respondents were strongly agreed that led to Decrease the quality of education and health services in the community and finally the tables shows 58 (58.6%) of the respondents were strongly agreed that unemployment due to Mass migration is an important cause for unemployment in urban areas. People migrate from rural areas in large groups when there is drought or when any other unfavorable conditions occur.

The study agreed by Rakotonirina, (2015) who said that Migration has its own positive and negative consequences on the place of departure and destination. Natural resource depletion, environmental pollution, earning disparities, redundancy, urban expansion, social unrest, population crowding were/are some of the negative effects of migration.

When I was conducting interview guide in the area of study with the question of what are the challenges facing migrants in urban areas respondents responds that there were „Natural resource depletion, environmental pollution, earning disparities, redundancy, urban expansion, social unrest, population crowding were/are some of the negative effects of migration““.

The research was required to look on the contribution of rural urban migration based on the finding, the researcher was identified weather there is the contribution to the ward cause by rural urban migration

Table 4.2.9 Contribution of Rural - Urban Migration

Introduction

The table below has showed if there is contribution of rural urban migration in Mikese and Wami Dakawa ward

Variables	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
Is there any contribution of Rural-urban Migration in your Ward?	80	80.8%	19	22.0%

Source: Field Data: (2025)

Most of the respondents were responds much on YES that 80 (80.8%) were agreed that there was contribution of Rural-urban Migration in your Ward in the sense that Subsidies for migration to cities can ease rural seasonal famines, and new roads from rural to urban areas can allow the uptake of more highly paid jobs, whilst also raising rural incomes.

Contribution of Rural-urban Migration

Introduction

The question asked that contribution of Rural-urban Migration the table tried to show the raising rural incomes improving electrical and communications infrastructure can do a lot to keep people out of cities by making markets more available to them. Improving roads between cities and towns is another way to help rural communities“ access urban markets

Table 4.3.10 Contribution of Rural-urban Migration

Variables	SD				D		U		A		S		A	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Improvement of living Standard	5	5.1	2	2.0	2	2.0	5	5.1	17	17.2	68	68.7		
Remittances	5	5.1	1	1.0	2	2.0	13	13.1	48	48.5	30	30.3		
Improvement of social services	5	5.1	0	0.0	1	1.0	10	10.1	36	36.4	47	47.5		
To alleviate Rural poverty	5	5.1	0	0.0	2	2.0	6	6.1	40	40.4	46	46.5		
Influence of Technology	5	5.1	1	1.0	2	2.0	15	15.2	41	41.4	35	35.4		

Source Field Data (2025)

The results shows that 68 (68.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed that there was Improvement of living standard the increasing share of a country's population that is living in places classed as "urban" is frequently, and appropriately, associated with rural-urban migration within the country, but differential rates of rural and urban fertility can affect this as well, 48 (48.5%) of the respondents were agreed that Remittances contributed much by Rural-urban Migration the urban to rural remittances.

The determinants of such financial flows and the use made in the rural areas of the money received, 47 (47.5%) of the respondents were strongly agreed that it led to the Improvement of social services, 46 (46.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed that to alleviate Rural poverty depend on Rural-urban Migration if the migrant have the notion of removing poverty rate when they reach in urban areas. And finally the table show the 41 (41.4%) of the respondents were agreed that Rural-urban Migration led to innovation of Technology, for one, represents a great opportunity. Essentially, technology innovation can be a crucial component of any effort to address needs and better serve individuals and families.

The study is with in agreement to Chukwuedozie, (2016) who commented that rural-urban migration has long been associated with economic development and growth in the economic literature. Also, include a decrease in infant mortality (half the rate in urban areas) and an increase in life expectancy (4 to 5 years longer in urban areas).

checklist for Focus Group Discussion about the following question and respondents responds that „*aware of the concept of rural-urban migration is the movement of people from rural areas to urban areas, the people who migrate in the ward were the poor people who move to urban areas with the notion of getting jobs in urban to reduce poverty level, reason for this migration are there was push factors influencing rural - urban migration among people the Rural push factors include poverty, inequitable land distribution, environmental degradation, high vulnerability to natural disasters, and violent conflicts while urban pull factors include better employment and education opportunities, higher income, diverse services, and less social discrimination in the cities. One respondent answers the question of the*

concept of poverty alleviation as the situation reduction or removing of poverty at individual or national level. And the benefit of remittances was the help to increase the standard of living of the families that receive them, help consumption of these families as a result, increasing national income and affecting DGP, it facilitates human capital investments particularly in increasing education of children, it helps provide food, clothing and health care, it has a direct effect on the recipient. The suggestions to improve the situation of poverty in your family or ward were to improve education level, expand national collection of tax revenue and other””. One of the respondents was claimed

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